

Distribution of resistance to ShB in F₂ of PI-Tetep, P₂-IET4699, P₃-Jawa no. 14, P₄-Yedao, and P₈-IR9752-71-3-2.

Analysis of variance in combining abilities of reactions to rice ShB, 1986.

Source of variation	DF	Sum of squares	Mean square	F values ^a	
				Model 1	2
General combining ability	7	16.0891	2.2984	257.67**	18.87**
Specific combining ability	20	10.5383	0.5269	59.07**	4.33**
Error Model 1	924		0.0089		
2	54		0.1218		

^a** = significant at 0.01.

without reciprocals among Tetep, IET4699, Mianhuatiao, Jawa no. 14, Yedao, 84-3019, Shuidaobawang, and IR9752-71-3-2 showed that general combining abilities were more prominent than specific combining abilities. That means that additive gene effects play a more important role in inheritance of resistance to ShB (see table). It would not be possible to derive

an elite line with a resistance level similar or superior to that of moderately resistant parents through recurrent selection. □

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A new inoculation technique for rice blast (BI)

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We studied a smear method for inoculating with the rice BI pathogen *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav. for resistance screening. Smear inoculation conditions are similar to natural infection.

The method requires only a small amount of spore suspension and gives a high infection frequency. Inoculation is carried out by smearing the mixture $1-2 \times 10^5$ conidia/ml suspended in 1-2% carboxymethyl cellulose onto the rice leaf with a brush.

The method is suitable for inoculation at several stages, but especially at the 2-4-leaf stage. A spore suspension of 1×10^5 conidia/ml gives nearly 100% leaf infection. Smear inoculation produces a higher disease index than spray inoculation, but lower than injection inoculation (Table 1).

This method also is useful as a simple and precise method for evaluating neck BI resistance (Table 2). □

Table 1. Effect of smear inoculation on leaf BI. Hangzhou, China, 1987.

Variety	BI index ^a			BI score ^b		
	Injection	Smear	Spraying	Injection	Smear	Spraying
<i>Indica</i>						
Chei-Tang	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nong 8506	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gui-Chao 2	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hou-Zeng-Zao	5.6	4.9	1.5	0.5	0.4	0.1
Zao-Shuang 1	14.8	14.3	4.0	1.3	1.3	0.4
Zhong 83-40	69.6	29.4	17.8	6.3	2.6	1.6
Zhong 83-49	76.4	68.6	45.5	6.9	6.2	4.1
Hong-Tu 3	86.9	71.2	48.9	7.8	6.4	4.4
B40	83.0	80.4	45.8	7.5	7.2	4.1
8004	96.9	73.9	48.3	8.7	6.6	4.4
Er-Jiu-Qing	95.1	85.8	53.5	8.6	7.7	4.8
Zuo 5	94.8	80.4	56.2	8.5	7.2	5.1
<i>Japonica</i>						
Pi-4	0	0	0	0	0	0
Kusabue	18.3	24.3	3.5	1.6	2.2	0.3
BL 1	87.2	52.4	41.0	7.8	4.7	3.7
Dong-Nong 363	71.8	68.6	42.7	6.5	6.2	3.8
Li-Jiang-Xing-Tuan-He-Guo	100.0	100.0	92.4	9.0	9.0	8.3

^aDisease index = $\frac{\sum(\text{number of plants with a given score} \times \text{value of that score})}{\text{total number of plants} \times \text{value of the highest score}}$

^bBased on Standard evaluation system for rice.

Table 2. Effect of smear inoculation on neck BI. Hangzhou, China, 1987.

Inoculation method	Plants (no.)	Plants with BI infection (no.)	Infection frequency (%)
Injection	10	10	100.00
Gear	22	22	100.00
Spraying	10	6	60.0

Rice sheath blotch incidence in Haryana

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Sheath blotch caused by *Pyrenochaeta oryzae* Shirai ex Miyake is increasing in

Resistance^a of rice varieties to sheath blotch in Kaul, India.

Lesion length (mm)	Group	Variety
10-15	1	IET7662, IET7738, IET7753, IR13420-6-3-3-1, IR17494-32-1-1-3-3, RP2151-21-1, RP2151-33-4, RP2151-7752, RP2240-86-84, CN758-1-1-1, UPR80-149.
15-30	2	Jaya, Ratna, HKR101, HAU3800-1, HAU3855-1, RP1832-23-34, RP2151-27-1.
30-45	3	HAU101-88, RP2151-76-1.
45-60	4	HAU47-6045-1, HAU101-60.
>60	5	IET7641, IR19661-23-3-2-2.

^a Resistant = groups 1 and 2, moderately resistant = group 3, susceptible = groups 4 and 5.

ricefields in Haryana. The disease appears as irregular and brownish lesions that enlarge and become sepia-colored. The middle portion of the lesion finally turns whitish and is studded with pycnidia, the characteristic symptom of the disease.

We conducted a roving survey 15-18 Oct 1986, when the rice crop was at the dough to maturity stage. Disease incidence was recorded on both sides of the road every 8 km. Of 52 villages, in Ambala, Jind, Karnal, and Kurukshetra districts, disease was found in 11 villages, more in Kurukshetra than in other districts. No disease was found in

Hisar and Sirsa districts. Disease incidence was higher on rice variety PR107, followed by Jaya, Basmati, and PR106.

Incidence on varieties or genotypes grown under field conditions at Haryana Agricultural University Rice Research Station, Kaul, was measured during 1986 wet season. Those varieties were categorized into five groupings on the basis of lesion length on the outer leaf sheath. Entries with lesion lengths 1-30 mm were categorized as resistant; 30-45 mm, moderately resistant; and more than 45 mm, susceptible (see table). □

Insect resistance

Registration of brown planthopper (BPH)-resistant germplasm lines in Japan

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Breeding to introduce the BPH resistance gene from indica to japonica rice varieties started in 1968. Since then, we have developed four japonica type lines, each with one of four different resistance genes (*Bph 1*, *bph 2*, *Bph 3*, and *bph 4*) (see table).

Norin PL 3, with the *Bph 1* gene, was selected from the cross F₆ 324/ Akitsuho // Tsukushibare. F₆ 324 is the donor parent, with *Bph 1* from Hoyoku/ Mudgo/2/ Kochikaze/3/ IR781-1-94/4/Hoyoku. In 1984, Norin PL 3 was registered as a germplasm line by the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, and Fisheries (MAFF), Japan.

Norin PL 4 inherited *bph 2* from IRI 154-243 through the cross combination of Asominori/ IRI 154-2431 / 2*Asominori. It was registered in 1985.

Norin PL 7 from the cross Tsukushibare *2/ Babawee inherited *bph*

Germplasm lines with BPH resistance.

Line	Resistance gene	Donor parent	Days to heading	Culm length (cm)
Norin PL 3	<i>Bph 1</i>	Mudgo	128	71
Norin PL 4	<i>bph 2</i>	IR1154-243	128	67
Norin PL 7	<i>bph 4</i>	Babawee	127	83
Norin PL 10	<i>Bph 3</i>	Rathu Heenati	131	80
Tsukushibare	—	—	130	73
Asominori	—	—	130	76

4 from Babawee. It was registered in 1987.

Norin PL 10, selected from the cross Tsukushibare/3/Tsukushibare*3/ Rathu Heenati /Tsukushibare, inherited *Bph 3* from Rathu Heenati. It was registered in 1988.

The antibiosis of these lines to BPH is similar to or slightly weaker than that of the donor indica varieties. The lines show inhibitory effect on BPH survival and population increase and different reactions to the biotypes.

Their morphological characteristics are mostly those of japonica varieties, except for a few traits, such as the amylose content of Norin PL 10.

When these lines are crossed with other japonica varieties, the F₁ does not show hybrid sterility, except with Norin PL 7. Partial seed sterility was observed in F₁ plants of Norin PL 7/a Japanese line.

These four lines are being used to breed BPH-resistant varieties in Japan. □

Rice resistance to whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) *Sogatella furcifera* in Bangladesh

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WBPH incidence has increased in recent years, particularly in the irrigated boro (Dec-Mar) crop. We screened BRRI varieties BR1-BR12 and BR14-BR21 and 22 IR varieties, using the standard seedbox test. TN1 was the susceptible check.

Seedlings (20/ 12-cm row) were infested with 2d- and 3d-instar nymphs